

MES-CoBraD

Multidisciplinary Expert System
for the Assessment & Management
of Complex Brain Disorders

D8.1

Report on the registration of the
Studies

September 2021

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www.mes-cobrad.eu

PREFACE

The Multidisciplinary Expert System for the Assessment & Management of Complex Brain Disorders (MES-CoBraD) is an interdisciplinary project combining Real-World Data (RWD) from multiple clinical and consumer sources through comprehensive, cost-efficient, and fast protocols towards improving diagnostic accuracy and therapeutic outcomes in people with Complex Brain Disorders (CoBraD), as reflected in Neurocognitive (Dementia), Sleep, and Seizure (Epilepsy) disorders and their interdependence.

- 1 It brings together internationally recognized experts in medicine, engineering, computer science, social health science, law, and marketing and communication from across Europe, and combines clinical information and scientific research in CoBraD with technical innovation in secure data-sharing platforms, artificial intelligence algorithms, and expert systems of precision and personalized care, with a primary focus on improving the quality of life of patients, their caregivers, and the society at large.
- 2 It leverages RWD from diverse CoBraD populations across cultural, socioeconomic, educational, and health system backgrounds, with special attention on including vulnerable populations and minorities in an equitable manner and engaging key stakeholders to maximize project impact.
- 3 The project will deliver a rigorous and self-standing methodology that will drive the MES-CoBraD implementation and define its operational principles; The MES-CoBraD solution, through the implementation of novel, self-standing AI based components and their integration under a common platform for scientific exploitation will assist focusing on the evaluation and validation of the solution, the spread of the excellence gained, the expansion of its ecosystem and the real-life sustainability.

CONSORTIUM

NTUA	National Technical University of Athens	EL
NIA	Neurological Institute of Athens	EL
HSCSP	Fundació privada Institut de Recerca de l'Hospital de la Santa Creu i Sant Pau	IR
VUB - LSTS	VRIJE UNIVERSITEIT BRUSSEL	BE
ups	UPPSALA UNIVERSITY	SE
RMC-C&E	Clalit Health Services- Rabin Medical Center Cognitive Neurology and Epilepsy Clinics	IL
kcl	King's College London	UK
HOLISTIC	HOLISTIC P.C.	EL
SIMAVI	Software Imagination & Vision	RO
LIBER	STICHTING LIBER	
ENG	Engineering - Ingegneria Informatica S.p.A.	EN
EVOLUTION	MICHOPOULOS I. & CH. G.P.	EL
UoE	University of Edinburgh	UK
CEL	CyberEthics Lab	IT

MULTIDISCIPLINARY EXPERT SYSTEM FOR THE ASSESSMENT & MANAGEMENT OF COMPLEX BRAIN DISORDERS

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Authors	Victor Montal
Contributors	-
Reviewers	LIBER, UEDIN

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1 INTRODUCTION

The registration of Observational and/or Interventional studies at the start of a project is a common practice in the medical field. The registration of the MES-CoBraD study, will make public the aims and goals of the project, the expected recruitment numbers and participant profiles and the (initial) scientific hypothesis. Our purpose in registering publicly the MES-CoBraD study is to be transparent (as a consortium). Moreover, the registration of the study would:

- › Promote the fulfilment of ethical obligations to participants
- › Provide information to potential participants and referring clinicians
- › Support adherence to scientific and ethical principles by providing a prospective declaration of the study's aims, hypotheses, analytical approaches and expected outcomes.

Moreover, entities and groups such as the International Committee of Medical Journal Editors (ICMJE) or the World Health Organization (WHO) increasingly encourage the registration of studies prior to their commencement.

2 BACKGROUND AND CURRENT STATUS

The registration of the MES-CoBraD study as an observational study, is a work in progress.

As a consortium, we initially decided to register our study in the context of the European Union trials, through the portal: <https://www.clinicaltrialsregister.eu/ctr-search/search> . However, we realised that the EU Clinical Trials Register only allows registration of interventional studies. While it is possible that a subgroup of scientific partners may decide, in the course of the project, to perform an interventional study, the project overall fits more with a description of an Observational Study. Thus, we decided to pivot the submission our project into the National Institutes of Health (USA) clinical trials register (<https://clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/home>), where the MES-CoBraD project fits the definition of Observational studies by NIH:

“The Observational Study Type (see Study Type data element on ClinicalTrials.gov) can be used to register studies of human beings in which biomedical and/or health outcomes are assessed in predefined groups of individuals, but the investigator does not assign specific interventions to the study participants.”

The registration of the project as an observational study, is a two-step process, led by Neurological Institute of Athens (NIA). First, the institution has to put in a request to obtain a Protocol Registration and Results System (PRS) account, to certify and authorise the institution to access the NIH clinical trials register. Afterwards, once the account is granted, the MES-CoBraD project will be registered as an observational study, with NIA as a general promoter and all the other centres as collaborators.

The information that must be included when registering the study includes:

- › **Study identification.** Detail the sponsor. Define the status of the project (on-going, ended, etc), detail the collaborators. Detail identification information.
- › **Study Description.** A detailed description of the study. This info should summarise the overall project, including the aims (and hypothesis).
- › **Observational Study Model.** Clarify if it's a cohort, case-control, family-based or case-only study.
- › **Time Perspective.**
- › **Biospecimen Retention and Description.** State if the project involves the retention of biosamples and define them.
- › **Enrolment.** Number of participants that will be included and the time participants will be follow-up.
- › **Outcome measure.** Define primary and secondary outcome measures. These should be related to the study description.
- › **Eligibility.** Criteria to include/exclude participants in the study.

The current status of the registration is that NIA has already obtained a PRS account and is in the process of filling the compulsory fields to submit the proposal as an Observational Study. Once the process is complete, the MES-CoBraD study will be searchable via the <https://clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/home> portal. Afterwards, the trials registration number will be shared with MES-CoBraD collaborators, and an Annex will be appended to this delivery, including a copy of the final registration form.

